

FAIR assessment

Disclaimer:

The test results shown here are based on preliminary data and code which still is under development. F-UJI is rapidly evolving and not yet available in a productive environment.

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Assessment Results:

Evaluated Resource:

NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository

✓ Save

↓ {JSON}

📄 New

FAIR level: ?

initial

Resource PID/URL:

https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf

DataCite support:	enabled
Metric Version:	metrics_v0.5
Metric Specification:	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6461229
Software version:	3.2.0
Download assessment results:	{JSON}
Save and share assessment results:	

Summary:

Report:

Findable

FsF-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.

FAIR level: 3 of 3

advanced

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "guid": "https:\\\\github.com\\Jenni0608\\NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository\\blob\\main\\nis2v_0ntc
  "guid_scheme": "url"
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-F1-01D-1	Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (IRI, URL)	1	3	
	test target: https://f-uji.net/vocab/identifier			
	condition: any of members of test target			
	tested on: https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/property/object_identifier			
	comment: identifier can be given as user input			
FsF-F1-01D-2	Identifier is not resolvable but follows an UUID or HASH type syntax	0		
	test target: https://f-uji.net/vocab/identifier/unique			
	specifically: name→uuid, hash			
	condition: any of <u>specified</u> members of test target			

tested on: https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/property/object_identifier
comment: identifier can be given as user input

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Using idutils schemes to identify unique or persistent identifiers for metadata
INFO	Starting assessment on identifier: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
SUCCESS	Unique identifier schemes found ['url']
INFO	Finalized unique identifier scheme - url

FsF-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.

FsF-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.

FAIR level: 1 of 3

initial

Score: 0.5 of 2

Output:

```
{
  "core_metadata_status": "some metadata",
  "core_metadata_found": {
    "summary": "NIS2V Vocabulary extending DPV to describe the NIS2 Cybersecurity risk-manage",
    "object_type": [
      "http://\schema.org/SoftwareSourceCode",
      "object"
    ]
  }
}
```

```

    ],
    "title": "NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository",
    "creator": "Jenni0608",
    "object_identifier": "https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob",
    "publisher": "GitHub"
  },
  "core_metadata_source": [
    [
      "DUBLINCORE_EMBEDDED",
      "html_embedding"
    ],
    [
      "MICRODATA_EMBEDDED",
      "microdata_rdfa"
    ],
    [
      "OPENGRAPH_EMBEDDED",
      "html_embedding"
    ]
  ]
}

```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-F2-01M-1	Metadata has been made available via common web methods	0.5	1	
<p>◀ test target: https://f-ujii.net/vocab/metadata/offering_method ▶</p> <p>condition: any of members of test target</p>				
FsF-F2-01M-2	Core data citation metadata is available	0		

test target: <https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/property>
specifically: *name*→creator, title, object_identifier, publication_date, publisher, object_type
condition: all of specified members of test target
tested on: https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/property

FsF-F2-01M-3

Core descriptive metadata is available

0

test target: <https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/property>
specifically: *name*→creator, title, object_identifier, publication_date, publisher, object_type, summary, keywords
condition: all of specified members of test target
tested on: https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/property

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Trying to resolve input URL -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Content negotiation on https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf accept=text/html, */*, status=200
INFO	Creating Cached response content
INFO	Found HTML page!
INFO	Typed links identification failed -:
INFO	Starting to analyse EMBEDDED metadata at -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Trying to identify EMBEDDED Microdata, OpenGraph or Schema.org -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-

	Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Trying to retrieve schema.org JSON-LD metadata from html page
INFO	Try to parse RDF (JSON-LD) from -: landing page
INFO	schema.org JSON-LD metadata in html page UNAVAILABLE
INFO	Trying to retrieve Dublin Core metadata from html page
SUCCESS	Found DublinCore metadata -: dict_keys(['summary'])
INFO	Trying to retrieve Microdata metadata from html page
INFO	Trying to extract Microdata metadata from -: MetadataSources.MICRODATA_EMBEDDED
SUCCESS	Found microdata metadata -: dict_keys(['object_type', 'title', 'creator'])
INFO	Trying to retrieve RDFa metadata from html page
INFO	Found RDF Graph which was successfully parsed
INFO	Trying to identify namespaces in RDF Graph
INFO	Could not find DCAT, schema.org or SKOS/OWL metadata, continuing with generic SPARQL
INFO	Trying to query generic SPARQL on RDF, found triples: -:33
INFO	Found RDFa like triples but at least some of them seem to be XHTML or OpenGraph properties which are excluded
INFO	Trying to retrieve Highwire and eprints metadata from html page
INFO	Highwire or eprints metadata UNAVAILABLE
INFO	Trying to retrieve OpenGraph metadata from html page
INFO	Found OpenGraph metadata -: dict_keys(['title', 'object_identifier', 'summary', 'object_type', 'publisher'])
INFO	Metadata property differs from metadata previously offered in a different formats -: title: NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository vs. NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/nis2v_Ontology_Final.r
SUCCESS	Found OpenGraph metadata -: dict_keys(['title', 'object_identifier', 'summary', 'object_type', 'publisher'])

INFO	Trying to identify Typed Links to data items in html page
INFO	Starting to identify EXTERNAL metadata through content negotiation or typed (signposting) links
INFO	Trying to retrieve XML metadata through content negotiation from URL -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Retrieving page -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf as application/xml, text/xml;q=0.5
INFO	Content negotiation on https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf accept=application/xml, text/xml;q=0.5, status=200
INFO	Creating Cached response content
INFO	Ignoring HTML response
INFO	Trying to extract/parse XML metadata from URL -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Expected XML but content negotiation responded -: MetadataFormats.HTML
INFO	Could not identify metadata properties in XML
INFO	Trying to retrieve schema.org JSON-LD metadata through content negotiation from URL -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Retrieving page -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf as application/ld+json
INFO	Content negotiation on https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf accept=application/ld+json, status=200
INFO	Creating Cached response content
INFO	Ignoring HTML response
INFO	Schema.org metadata through content negotiation UNAVAILABLE

INFO	Trying to retrieve RDF metadata through content negotiation from URL -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
INFO	Retrieving page -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf as text/turtle, application/turtle, application/x-turtle;q=0.8, application/rdf+xml, text/n3;q=0.9, text/rdf+n3;q=0.9,application/ld+json
INFO	Content negotiation on https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf accept=text/turtle, application/turtle, application/x-turtle;q=0.8, application/rdf+xml, text/n3;q=0.9, text/rdf+n3;q=0.9,application/ld+json, status=200
INFO	Creating Cached response content
INFO	Ignoring HTML response
INFO	Try to parse RDF from -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf as turtle
WARNING	Failed to parse RDF -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf exactly one of source, location, file or data must be given
INFO	Linked Data metadata UNAVAILABLE
INFO	Trying to retrieve datacite metadata
INFO	Retrieving page -: https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf as application/vnd.datacite.datacite+json
INFO	Content negotiation on https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf accept=application/vnd.datacite.datacite+json, status=200
INFO	Creating Cached response content
INFO	Ignoring HTML response
INFO	Datacite metadata UNAVAILABLE

INFO	Type of object described by the metadata -: ['http://schema.org/SoftwareSourceCode', 'object']
INFO	Testing if any metadata has been made available via common web standards
INFO	Found some descriptive metadata elements -: dict_keys(['summary', 'object_type', 'title', 'creator', 'object_identifier', 'publisher'])
WARNING	Not all required citation metadata elements exist, missing -: ['publication_date']
INFO	Will exclusively consider community specific metadata properties which are specified in metrics -: {'name': ['creator', 'title', 'object_identifier', 'publication_date', 'publisher', 'object_type', 'summary', 'keywords']}
WARNING	Not all required core descriptive metadata elements exist, missing -: ['publication_date', 'keywords']

FsF-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.

FsF-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved programmatically.

FAIR level: 3 of 3

advanced

Score: 1 of 2

Output:

```
{
  "search_mechanisms": [
    {
      "mechanism": "structured data",
      "mechanism_info": [
        "dublin-core via: html_embedding",
        "schemaorg via: microdata_rdfa"
      ]
    }
  ]
}
```

```

    ]
  }
]
}

```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-F4-01M-1	Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa)	1	3	
	<p>test target: http://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/standard</p> <p>specifically: <i>name</i>→dublin-core, schemaorg, dcat-data-catalog-vocabulary</p> <p>condition: any of <u>specified</u> members of test target</p> <hr/> <p>test target: http://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/offering_method</p> <p>specifically: <i>name</i>→html_embedding, microdata_rdfa</p> <p>condition: any of <u>specified</u> members of test target</p>			
FsF-F4-01M-2	Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite)	0		

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Will exclusively consider community specific metadata standards for FsF-F4-01M-1 which are specified in metrics -: ['dublin-core', 'schemaorg', 'dcat-data-catalog-vocabulary']

INFO	Will exclusively consider community specific metadata offering methods for FsF-F4-01M-1 which are specified in metrics -: ['html_embedding', 'microdata_rdfa']
SUCCESS	Metadata is offered in a way major search engines can ingest it -: ['dublin-core via: html_embedding', 'schemaorg via: microdata_rdfa']
WARNING	Google Search Cache DB does not exist, see F-UJI installation instructions
INFO	Identifier not listed in Google Dataset Search cache -: ['https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf']
INFO	Querying Mendeley Data API for -:https://github.com/Jenni0608/NIS2V-Vocabulary-Repository/blob/main/nis2v_Ontology_Final.rdf
WARNING	Metadata is NOT found through registries considered by the assessment service -: ['DATACITE', 'MENDELEY_DATA', 'GOOGLE_DATASET']

Interoperable

FsF-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.

FsF-I2-01M - Metadata uses semantic resources

FsF-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.

Reusable

FsF-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.

FAIR level: 1 of 3

initial

Score: 1 of 4

Output:

```
{
  "object_type": "object",
  "data_content_descriptor": []
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1-01MD-1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	1	1	
a	Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata	0		
b	Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata	0		
FsF-R1-01MD-2	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	0		
a	File size and type information are specified in metadata	0		
b	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata	0		

FsF-R1-01MD-3	Data content matches file type and size specified in metadata	0	
FsF-R1-01MD-4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata	0	

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Object landing page accessible status -: None
SUCCESS	Valid resource type (e.g. subtype of schema.org/CreativeWork, DCMI Type or DataCite resourceType) specified -: softwaresourcecode
SUCCESS	Valid resource type (e.g. subtype of schema.org/CreativeWork, DCMI Type or DataCite resourceType) specified -: object
WARNING	NO data object content available/accessible to perform file descriptors (type and size) tests

FsF-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.

FsF-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.

FAIR level: 2 of 3 moderate

Score: 1 of 2

Output: {
 "provenance_metadata_included": {
 "is_available": true,

```

    "provenance_metadata": [
      {
        "prov_o_mapping": "prov:wasAttributedTo",
        "metadata_element": "creator",
        "metadata_value": "Jenni0608"
      },
      {
        "prov_o_mapping": "prov:wasAttributedTo",
        "metadata_element": "publisher",
        "metadata_value": "GitHub"
      }
    ]
  },
  "structured_provenance_available": {
    "is_available": false,
    "provenance_metadata": []
  }
}

```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1.2-01M-1	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV	1	2	
FsF-R1.2-01M-2	Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O)	0		

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	Check if provenance information is available in descriptive metadata
INFO	Check if provenance information is available in metadata about related resources

WARNING	No provenance information found in metadata about related resources
SUCCESS	Found data creation-related provenance information
INFO	Check if provenance specific namespaces are listed in metadata
WARNING	Formal provenance metadata is unavailable

FsF-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.

FAIR level: 1 of 3

initial

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
[
  {
    "metadata_standard": "Dublin Core",
    "url": "http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/",
    "subject_areas": [
      "sciences"
    ],
    "type": "generic",
    "source": [
      "https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m15",
      "https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.3nx7t",
      "http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/dublin-core"
    ]
  },
  {
    "metadata_standard": "Schema.org",
    "url": "http://schema.org/",
    "subject_areas": [
```

```

        "sciences"
    ],
    "type": "generic",
    "source": [
        "https://doi.org/10.25504/FAIRsharing.hzdzq8",
        "https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/msc/m101"
    ]
}
]

```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-R1.3-01M-1	Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs	0		
	<p>test target: https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/standards</p> <p>specifically: <i>field_of_science</i>→science, generic</p> <p>condition: any except of <u>specified</u> members of test target</p> <p>comment: test performed on namespaces or schemas found in exposed metadata</p>			
FsF-R1.3-01M-2	Community specific metadata standard is listed in the re3data record of the responsible repository	0		
	<p>test target: https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/standards</p> <p>specifically: <i>field_of_science</i>→science, generic</p> <p>condition: any except of <u>specified</u> members of test target</p> <p>comment: test is performed using information collected from re3data</p>			

FsF- R1.3- 01M-3 Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, fairsharing) standard is listed in the re3data record or detected by namespace 1 1

test target: <https://f-uji.net/vocab/metadata/standards>

specifically: *field_of_science*→science, *genericsource*→rd-alliance.org, fairsharing.org

condition: any of specified members of test target

Debug messages:

Level:	Message:
INFO	re3data/datacite client id -: None
INFO	Namespaces included in the metadata -: ['http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/', 'http://ogp.me/ns#', 'http://schema.org/']
INFO	Found non-disciplinary standard (but RDA listed) -: via ns: Dublin Core - http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/
INFO	Found disciplinary standard -: via ns : The Open Graph protocol metadata format - http://ogp.me/ns#
INFO	Found non-disciplinary standard (but RDA listed) -: via ns: Schema.org - http://schema.org/
INFO	Retrieving API and Standards
INFO	No Datacite client id found, therefore skipping re3data metadata retrieval
WARNING	NO valid OAI-PMH endpoint found
SUCCESS	Found non-disciplinary standards (but RDA listed) using namespaces or schemas found in re3data record or via provided metadata or metadata services outputs

FsF-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.

Accessible

FsF-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.

FsF-A1-03D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.

FsF-A1-02M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.

FAIR level: 3 of 3

advanced

Score: 1 of 1

Output:

```
{
  "standard_metadata_protocol": {
    "https": {
      "name": "Hyper Text Transfer Protocol Secure"
    }
  }
}
```

Metric tests:

Test:	Test name:	Score:	Maturity:	Result:
FsF-A1-02M-1	Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols.	1	3	

**Debug
messages:**

Level:	Message:
SUCCESS	Standard protocol for access to metadata found -: https
INFO	NOT all required metadata given, see: FsF-F2-01M

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